

The First Australian Trained Doctors. Patrick Moloney (1843-1904). Part One: The Clinical Career

Peter Stride

MBBS, MRCP(UK), FRACP, FRCPEdin, FRCP, D. Med - research (UQ);
Senior Lecturer, University of Queensland School of Medicine, Australia

Suggested Citation

Stride, P. (2024). The First Australian Trained Doctors. Patrick Moloney (1843-1904). Part One: The Clinical Career. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 981-1006.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).87](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).87)

Abstract:

In 1867, William Carey Rees and Patrick Maloney were the first two medical students to graduate from an Australian Medical School. Prior to that date all medical practitioners working in Australia since the First Fleet in 1788 had graduated overseas, predominantly in England and Scotland. The distinguished career of Dr Patrick Moloney, physician and writer, is described. Part, one deals with his clinical cases and career as a physician.

Keywords: *history, Australian medicine, Patrick Moloney, career.*

Introduction

The Melbourne Medical School opened in 1862 after the Sydney University School of Medicine opened in 1856, but before Sydney admitted its first medical students. Melbourne admitted its first medical students in 1862. In 1867, Patrick Moloney was one of the first two students to qualify as a doctor from an Australian Medical School and his distinguished career is described. The major source of information is the National Library of Australia digitised newspapers, the Trove website. This is not a peer reviewed source but contains the most available information.

Care was taken to distinguish Dr William Maloney from Dr Patrick Moloney as William often appears in the press misspelt as Moloney. Maloney, a St Mary's graduate in London in 1885, became a Member of Parliament in 1889. Though only practising medicine for four years he claimed to be a medical expert! William's other most dubious claim to fame was being the longest serving back bencher, ie never achieving cabinet status!

Figure 1. University of Melbourne

Dr. Patrick Moloney was born in Ireland, the son of James Moloney and his wife Catherine, née Kelly in 1843, and migrated to Port Phillip, Australia with his family as a boy. Following schooling at St. Patrick's College, Melbourne, he was one of three students to enter the new Medical School of the Melbourne University in 1862. In 1867 Moloney and William Carey Rees were the first students in Australia to graduate in medicine.

University Career

Moloney distinguished himself in areas other than medicine. In 1862 he also studied arts, winning second-class honours as well as the classics and logic exhibition. He was first in arts in 1862 and 1863. In 1866 he won the Vice-Chancellor's Prize for an English essay. He matriculated with credit and was exhibitioner in classics. His skill in creative writing continued through his life. Moloney also displayed talent in medicine gaining first-class honours in the third and fourth years of the medical course. He graduated in 1867 MB with William Carey Rees, the first two graduates of Melbourne University, the first graduates of any Australian medical school, and was added to the list of fully qualified medical practitioners (The Herald, 1867).

Figure 2. Patrick Moloney

Medical Career

One autumn day Moloney arrived at the hospital and said 'Do you know what I should like to be

doing today? A drive into the country behind a good spanking horse, a good cigar in my mouth, a bottle of whiskey under the seat, and that girl in red from the Gaiety by my side'.

Clinical Cases

Edward Fletcher, Ms Robinson and two brothers named Denis and Michael Clifford fell out in a drinking session and a knife fight ensued. They were taken to hospital where Dr Moloney and another dressed their wounds. Denis Clifford was so severely stabbed over the eye that he was detained in the Hospital. Michael Clifford has three wounds in the head, Fletcher has two wounds in the leg, and a cut on the head from a blow of a candlestick and the woman had one cut in the head (The Herald, 1868).

Dr Moloney attended Ellen Earl, aged thirty-three years, with abdominal stab wounds, however she refused to remain at the hospital. According to her statement, a man whom she did not know came up to her and said, "You are a friend of mine," at the same time putting his hand up her clothes and stabbing her.

The description of the man given to the police was most complete and minute in each particular, so the Herald expected that the offender would soon be in custody (The Riverina Herald, 1869).

Dr. Moloney attended Mary Lacey, a widow, following a desperate attempt at suicide in which she cut her throat, but only superficially. She was progressing as favourably as can be expected (Weekly Times, 1869).

Dr Moloney attended Mary Tucker, a young domestic servant woman with severe burns to the upper portion of her body sustained when her place of employment, a shop in Butke St., caught alight. Twenty six houses were damaged by the fire. Her condition appeared very desperate when she reached the hospital. The body was pulseless and cold, there were severe burns on the back, on both arms, and both legs. Following repeated application of stimulants, she came round gradually to consciousness and appeared to improve before a sudden deterioration and her death (Geelong Advertiser, 1870; The Herald, 1870).

Dr Moloney attended John Moore when he was taken to hospital following a fight in which Moore sustained a severe head injury from the sharp edge of a hand saw. Moloney found teeth marks in the scalp from the saw and a fractured skull. Initially Moloney feared the injury would be fatal, but Moore recovered slowly being discharged after seven weeks and was able to return to work (The Age, 1870a; The Argus, 1870a).

Dr. Moloney attended Thomas Cleary with a severe scalp laceration sustained during a brawl in a brothel in which a glass tumbler was thrown at his head and broke. Witnesses stated that the blood loss was severe and Moloney according to the press stated that five minutes more blood loss could have been fatal. Cleary appears to be responding well to treatment (Weekly Times, 1870).

A patient in the Melbourne Hospital casualty stole £9 from Dr. Moloney, as the paper stated that was not the common practice of persons who are admitted to the hospital casualty to show their gratitude for free attendance (Australasian, 1870).

Dr Moloney was summoned to the New York Hotel, 17 Bourke Street West to see James Robinson, a nineteen year old young man, who had been taken ill the night before and the following morning appeared to be dying. Moloney arrived too late and expressed the opinion that the man had died from natural causes.

A bottle containing medicine was found in his room, and on his person was found a paper signed by John Stanway recommending James Robinson for admission to the Melbourne Hospital. The body was removed to the morgue (The Argus, 1872b).

Mr. Michael Costello, a farmer from Tallarook was admitted to the Kilmore Hospital under Dr Moloney with a fractured femur sustained when his horse drawn vehicle crashed into a tree. Moloney and Dr Semple, the house surgeon performed an amputation, presumably for a compound injury, and Costello died shortly after surgery leaving a widow and eleven children (The Argus, 1873).

Dr Moloney attended Mr Fosse after a riding accident in which he was kicked by his horse. He suffered concussion and injuries to his throat and spine. Moloney sutured the throat laceration and it was hoped he would make an uneventful recovery (The Telegraph, St Kilda Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1874; Weekly Times, 1874).

Dr. Ferguson presented the case of a little girl, aged about two to the Medical Society of Victoria, who had been bitten on the ankle by a tiger snake then treated for shock with intravenous injections of ammonia. Dr Moloney supported this argument though some traditionalists favoured the old ligature, cut and suck method (The Age, 1876a).

Mr. Fitzgerald, Dr. Moloney, and Mr. Knagge operated on Mr. Woods, a politician, with a ruptured cerebral vessel. Apparently he was subsequently progressing favourably. This sounds amazing that presumably a craniotomy and ligature of a vessel could be successfully undertaken in 1876 (The Argus, 1876a).

Dr Moloney cared for Mr. George Petty during his terminal serious but unspecified illness. Though Moloney considered his condition hopeless, Petty and his many friends were hopeful when he had a brief rally before he passed away peacefully in the presence of his family (The Australasian, 1877).

Mr G. P. Smith, while engaged in a case in the County Court, was suddenly taken ill. Dr Moloney was summoned and ordered Smith to be removed to his house. No further clinical nor prognostic details were given (The Herald, 1877).

Dr. Moloney attended a young man named Dean, who was knocked down and run over by a fire engine. He received severe contusions about the head. Every attention. was paid to .the unfortunate young fellow but he died that night from the injuries received (Geelong Advertiser, 1878).

Dr Moloney was summoned to see a Matthew Higgins who was perched on a ledge on top of the Hotel di Roma threatening to jump or cut his throat. Higgins was eventually forced down and

arrested. In his possession were a revolver, some silver, and eight "keep your temper coins," used as gambling tokens in whist, and a certificate from Dr Moloney, stating that a Mr Higgins was suffering from bronchitis. While being searched the man cried out for Dr Moloney and seemed to fear that he was going to be killed (The Argus, 1878a; Mercury and Weekly Courier, 1878).

Dr Moloney attended the eleven year old son of Mr Heyward, a draper. He had fallen off a fence onto a large boulder dislocating his shoulder which was initially relocated by Dr Reed. However when the boy developed a lump on his shoulder, he was taken to Moloney who pronounced the case a very serious one, the shoulder cap being split, and therefore rendering the limb perfectly useless to the lad for life, as it cannot be repaired. Very few cases of this kind have occurred, according to the doctor's statement. Such a lesion should not challenge an orthopaedic surgeon today, maybe Heyward should have sought a second opinion (The Herald, 1878b)!

Dr. Moloney attended Mr. J. D. Mahony during his terminal illness. Although only thirty six, he had been in failing health for some years, with death considered inevitable in the last eight months. He left a widow but no children (Williamstown Chronicle, 1878).

Dr Moloney and many of his medical colleagues were summoned to examine the Hon. Graham Berry, Chief Secretary, Treasurer, and Minister of War following a fall head foremost into the hold of the steam tender when disembarking from Her Majesty's Colonial warship Nelson. Initial reports indicated that he had fallen onto his head, but on his arrival at his arrival at Williamstown, it was telegraphed that his legs had been seriously abraded by violent contact with the starboard gunwale.

Opinions, reproduced below, were not always serious and the press enjoyed their report of the event.

Dr. Moloney considers Mr. Berry in a fit state to go home, provided he goes quietly, and does not overtax himself mentally or physically. He should go on a long sea voyage by a slow ship, thus avoiding Mentone and Paris, and he should

not on any account have a fast rattling and convivial companion.

Dr. McCrae, Chief Medical Officer, thought both legs were radically weak, and recommended Mr. Berry should not attempt to stand up on platforms, decks, or gunwales for some time to come.

Dr. Spyzle Maynebraze, (Surgeon, H.M.S. Nelson!), has carefully examined the Minister of War's lower spars, and considers the starboard one a little sprung. He thinks he could mend it by splints and a rope yarn in three months but will not undertake to effect a cure unless Mr. Berry pledges himself to give up drinking spirituous liquors.

Dr. Bigg has considered the case carefully, and is certain that erysipelas is getting in. He recommends immediate amputation of both limbs. Two others advised immediate amputation but of different legs.

Berry appeared back at work the following day and was planning visits to Paris and London, the injury cannot have been too severe (Melbourne Punch, 1878b; The Herald, 1878a).

Father Daniel Lordan, aged sixty six, one of the curates at St. Francis' Church was attended by Dr. Moloney during his terminal illness for which no clinical details were given. His obituary was full of praise for his deep theological knowledge and his truly devout service to the communities of Ireland, Victoria and the West Indies (Advocate, 1879).

Maude Mein, a healthy little girl, aged between five and six, was attended by Dr Moloney following a fall in her yard in which she struck her head heavily against the ground and went into convulsions. Moloney found the child in a semi-insensible condition, but, under treatment, she rallied for a few hours, only to die later that afternoon. Presumably, she suffered a cerebral haemorrhage, though why only some are operated upon remains obscure (The Herald, 1879).

Mary Prensler was admitted to the Melbourne Hospital under Dr Moloney with an internal issue. Moloney advised a 'delicate operation' which Mary requested to be performed in the

Women's Hospital. Unfortunately, she was informed there were no beds available there and the unfortunate woman was then bounced around for a few days between the two hospitals and several doctors, and the police cells before being finally admitted to the Women's Hospital on the third presentation in a state of hysteria and faintness (The Herald, 1880).

Dr Moloney attended some of the injured survivors from a fatal train crash in which three men died. Mr. A. E. Moore was found to have fractured his left arm both above and below the elbow. He had also sustained a slight injury to the head causing significant pain. His arm wound became infected with a discharge of pus and his fractures could not be set until the infection diminished. This sounds like an infected compound fracture for which amputation was often necessary in 1881.

Dr Moloney examined Bruce Gaunson with both doctor and patients describing his injuries. He had bruises all over his body, besides several very severe lacerations. The left leg was particularly bruised and that there were signs of inflammation over the shin bone. The right thigh was also severely bruised, the back is bruised, and a piece of the muscle has been torn off the angle of the shoulder blade. After the shock he received Gaunson said he lost his eyesight totally for a period.

Mr Alexander had symptoms of concussion of the spine and partial paralysis of the upper extremities, but it was expected to be of a temporary nature. He was suffering very severely from the shock to the system, but he was not considered to be in any immediate danger.

Moloney treated Mr N. C. McKellar, but no details of his injuries were given. Moloney and all the other treating doctors were asked to act on behalf of the department and examine all the cases so as to accurately determine the injury each individual has sustained, presumably for compensation purposes (The Age, 1881a; The Argus, 1881c; 1881d; Illustrated Australian News, 1881).

Two young ladies, Miss Mason and Miss Young were driving a pair of ponies on the Heidelberg Road when the animals took fright and bolted.

Miss Mason imprudently jumped out of the vehicle, and fell on her head, sustaining concussion of the brain. Miss Young was also injured, but not so seriously. Dr Moloney attended Miss Mason whose condition was reported as being very critical (Gippsland Mercury, 1881).

Drs. Moloney attended Mr. Brooke Smith, Inspector of Police, who had been confined to his bed for a few days suffering from very severe illness. His condition was such as to cause the gravest apprehension as the patient was in an exceedingly critical condition, and in fact he did not survive (The Age, 1882c; The Herald, 1882).

Dr. Moloney attended a Mr Brodie, recently arrived from Assam in India. He died from presumed Tuberculosis soon after arrival and Moloney considered an inquest unnecessary (Weekly Times, 1882).

Dr Moloney attended Mrs. Lawler who suffered a spinal injury in a train accident and was confined to bed suffering from prolonged shock. Her young son was also suffering severely through the shock to his nervous system (The Age, 1882b; The Leader, 1882).

Moloney considered Mr. Parry, a shopkeeper, was suffering from shock following a train accident (The Age, 1882b).

Dr. Moloney attended Mr. Kavanagh, another train crash victim and considered that Kavanagh was not yet out of danger, although he was slowly improving (The Argus, 1882a).

Dr. Moloney treated Mr. Beck, yet another train crash victim, who had the top of his right shoulder and some ribs broken. Beck progressed favourably until pleuro-pneumonia set in (The Argus, 1882b).

Dr Moloney was summoned but unable to attend a train crash at Newmarket on the Essendon line. Drs. Williams and Ryan attended to the twenty mild to moderate injured travellers from this low impact collision (The Argus, 1883a).

Dr. Moloney examined the damaged hand of Mick Nathan, the boxer, finding the injury to be much more severe than was at first anticipated,

and Moloney issued a medical certificate stating that he will be unable to use his hand for boxing for some weeks (Sportsman, 1883).

Dr. Moloney attended Mr. J. D. Thompson in the Sydney Hotel, William Street following his injury in the Little River railway disaster. Thompson had the ligaments of the right knee torn, and the leg was greatly swollen. He had severe pains in the chest, presumed to have been caused by a portion of the wood work of the carriage pressing upon him (The Age, 1884a).

Dr Moloney attended a boy about twelve yours of ago, whose name was initially unknown who met with a serious accident in Fitzroy. He fractured his clavicle when hurrying to his work and falling down (The Herald, 1884c).

Mr Freeman was admitted to the Melbourne Hospital with a vesicular rash which Drs Moloney and Fulton diagnosed confidently as smallpox, though modified by previous vaccination. On the other hand Drs Youl and Llewelyn believed it was chicken pox. The press was delighted to mock the doctors for their inability to achieve a common correct diagnosis. No details of the distribution of the rash to the palms of the hands and soles of the feet are given, even at an interview with Moloney, to enable a reader's opinion. All agreed the vesicles were resolving and the patient recovering (The Herald, 1884b; The Riverina Herald, 1884; The Herald, 1884a).

Dr Moloney attended a lad named George Zeplin following a serious accident falling from a ladder while playing with a companion in a bakehouse. He fell from a height of about seven feet against a stone trough, which caused concussion of the brain and a fractured skull. He lay in a critical state at his father's residence.

A year later he won a school music prize so must have recovered completely (The Age, 1884c; The Australasian, 1885).

Dr. Patrick Moloney cared for the renowned author, Marcus Clarke, during his terminal illness when aged only thirty five. Marcus Andrew Hislop Clarke was born at Kensington, the Old Court suburb of London on the 24th April. A sickly infant with an ankylosed left arm, his

health improved although the arm remained permanently shrunken, he retained through life a slight stammer.

The illness which caused his death commenced with an attack of pleurisy and this developing into congestion of the liver, and finally into erysipelas, which carried him off in the space of a short week. Indeed from the beginning Moloney held out little hope, as his constitution was utterly worn out, and the mental worry of the latter weeks had completed the task of dissolution. But the dying man himself did not evidently realise his position, even up to the time of the insensibility which preceded death (The Age, 1884d).

Moloney attended Peter Newton a renowned wrestler who was confined to bed with a non-specified illness but was gradually getting better and expected to be about at the end of the week under the care and kindness of Dr. Moloney (Sportsman, 1884).

The Rev. P. Kearns expressed his gratitude to his parishioners and my brother priests for their warm sympathy during a long illness following an accident. He also expressed his deepest gratitude to Dr. Moloney who came to attend him free of charge (Advocate, 1885b).

A terrible catastrophe occurred in the race for the Caulfield Cup, resulting in one jockey, Donald Nicholson, being killed on the spot, while at least six others were seriously injured.

Fortunately, there were a number of medical gentlemen on the ground, and Drs. Fitzgerald, Moloney, J. Williams and others at once placed their services at the disposal of the sufferers. A brief examination revealed that Cracknell had his sternum broken and other severe internal injuries. O'Grady was insensible with a broken shoulder and nose. Wyman sustained a fracture of the skull, and McGrath was suffering from concussion of the brain. Tuomey, who's horse was killed, was very badly hurt. Others were severely shaken but uninjured.

As soon after the accident as possible O'Grady, McGrath, Cracknell and Tuomey were taken to the Melbourne Hospital, and Wyman to the Alfred Hospital, where they were attended to,

and where they were reported to have gone on improving (The Age, 1885c).

A former patient of Dr Moloney's, Mr Peter Bradley, died suddenly. He had been under medical treatment for some time past for affection of the heart, and Dr. Moloney had informed him some time back his sudden demise may be expected any moment (Kilmore Free Press, 1886).

Dr Moloney resumed his medical practice at his former address a few days after his return from Europe (Advocate, 1887).

Dr. Moloney treated two children, named Lucy and Violet Wright, aged respectfully two and seven years, who were taken to the Melbourne Hospital, displaying every symptoms of poisoning. The contents of their stomachs having been analysed by the Government analyst they were found to contain arsenide of copper used in the green colouring of some biscuits.

The manufacturers withdrew the biscuits, refunded their customers and proceedings were most likely be instituted against the manufacturers (Weekly Times, 1887).

An elderly man named Thomas Donovan died under circumstances which gave rise to an impression that a serious change in connection with his case might lie at the door of the impostor Hartley, the vendor of the so-called Prairie Flower remedy, or the tooth drawing woman by whom Hartley was accompanied.

It seems that about three weeks ago Donovan went to see Hartley and colleague, and had a tooth drawn after her usual fashion. Next day he suffered such agony in the jaw that he went to the hospital and was there told his jaw had been seriously injured. After being treated for some time as an outside patient and not recovering, he consulted Dr. Moloney, who at once ordered him to bed and stated that besides other ailments, not connected with the tooth extraction, there was serious inflammation of the jaw. Donovan remained under treatment for several days until he died. Having been informed of the circumstances as to how the injuries to the jaw were inflicted, Dr Moloney at first hesitated to give a certificate of death, but further

examination convinced him that he was justified in doing so, and the certificate was given in the morning, and the deceased buried this afternoon. It is surprising an inquest did not follow with a possible charge of culpable negligence (The Herald, 1887).

Dr Moloney attended an eleven year old boy named Seymour Larnier after he was run over by a tram and dragged along several feet before the tram was stopped. He was conveyed to Dr Moloney's nearby residence, where it was found that one of his legs and his clavicle were broken. He was also shockingly bruised and was bleeding from wounds on the face.

Dr Moloney stated that there was no reason to anticipate a serious result from the injuries and a full recovery was expected. He was subsequently taken to the Botanical Hotel, where his parents resided (The Argus, 1887a; The Age, 1887a).

Dr. Moloney attended William W. Low, an accountant, who was crossing the road when he was knocked down by a tram. He was picked up unconscious, with a severe wound on his head and was taken to Moloney as the nearest surgeon, After tending to his injuries, Moloney sent him to the Melbourne Hospital in charge of Constable M. Kelly. After Low had recovered his senses, being intoxicated, he was removed to the lock-up (The Argus, 1887c).

Dr. Moloney attended the Town Clerk of Melbourne, Mr. E. G. Fitzgibbon with a fractured rib. Whilst endeavouring to land at Philip Island he lost his footing and fell heavily on a rock.

He was progressing favourably resting at home and hoped to be able to return to his official duties in the course of another week (The Age, 1888b).

Dr. Beaney and Dr. Moloney successfully removed a bullet from the scapular area of Constable Stokes following a shooting in central Melbourne. Stokes was making an arrest when the gun was fired. He is expected to make an uneventful recovery but the unknown perpetrator remained at large in the city (The Argus, 1888).

Dr. Moloney attended Mr Le Gould the recently appointed secretary and surveyor of the Barrabool shire council, certifying that he was dangerously ill with inflammation of the liver. In the era before pathological particularly virology and scans of the liver, diagnoses are too numerous to list.

This caused the council some inconvenience but it may also have inconvenienced Le Gould, especially since he died the following month from a liver abscess! An operation was performed by Drs. Beane and Moloney a few days prior to Mr. Le Gould's demise, with the view of giving him relief, but his strength having become exhausted he was unable to rally (Geelong Advertiser, 1888; Colac Herald, 1889).

Dr. Moloney attended Mr. Henry Keiley during his terminal illness with congestion of the brain and gout.

Keiley was born in London in 1831 and nurtured among musical surroundings. He was best known in journalistic and musical circles as the highly respected musical critic of *The Argus* for upwards of twenty years (*The Australasian*, 1889; *The Argus*, 1889b).

Dr Moloney was summoned to see a Mrs McAdam who collapsed suddenly in Collins St.

But she had died almost instantly and there was nothing Moloney could do. He was of the opinion that she had died from dropsy as she was stout and reported as short of breath, though the presence or absence of oedema is not reported. Moloney was prepared to issue a death certificate and thought an inquest unnecessary (*Herald*, 1889).

A severe influenza epidemic struck Melbourne through March and April dominating the media. Dr. Moloney stated that in his ward in the Melbourne Hospital there are several cases under treatment and that there are three kinds of influenza : — 1, The nervous, most likely to produce latona. (Latona is a Greek goddess of motherhood, the meaning is unclear) 2. Gastro-intestinal, which may easily be confounded with typhoid, being so like it as to become irregular and abortive towards the end. 3. Inspiratory,

which produces broncho-pneumonia, known also as the fog fever.

The period of incubation is two days, and when it starts it develops itself in a few hours, the temperature going often as high as 105°F, its symptoms being "cold in the head," backache, and extreme physical and mental depression, and general rheumatic or neuralgic pains. The numerous remedies recommended by many specialists testified to the lack of any effective remedy at that time.

By mid-April the number of persona applying for admission at the Melbourne Hospital as suffering from influenza was decreasing. A large number of nurses and porters were down with the complaint, but the medical staff were the most afflicted, and most of them were incapacitated for work. Dr. Moloney stated that the broncho-pneumonia or lung complication cases are very bad at present, and also very common and serious (*Weekly Times*, 1890b; *Weekly Times*, 1890a).

Dr. P. Moloney attended Mr. Peter Cameron who became unwell with typhoid fever three weeks previously. After initial improvement he succumbed to the illness at the age of twenty four in spite of the limited therapy available at the time and unremitting nursing attendance. In this era, the mortality of typhoid was about 20% (*Stride*, 2015; *Williamstown Chronicle*, 1890a).

Dr Moloney treated Alderman O'Grady, who had been prostrated for some time with a serious 'attack of inflammation.' After an initial considerable change for the better, he deteriorated and died two weeks later at the age of sixty six (*The Age*, 1890; *Leader*, 1890).

Moloney attended a most unfortunate forty two year old woman, Bridget Keely, who had suffered from increasingly severe elephantiasis for some eight or nine years. She was an unwanted homeless vagrant.

She had been an inpatient in the Melbourne Hospital but was discharged as incurable. The Alfred Hospital with a section for incurables refused to admit her. Her malodorous lesions made her undesirable to all institutions including

Christian charities. She ended up begging to be sent to jail (The Herald, 1890a)

Dr Moloney attended Mr William Sheean, an iron founder, who was a victim of another train crash. Moloney considered Sheean was affected by the shock and advised him to seek complete rest till his nerves were restored to their normal condition.

The Argus considered the case was not serious and anticipated a speedy recovery (The Argus, 1890)!

A middle aged woman named Elizabeth Harris was admitted under Dr Moloney to the hospital while suffering from the effects of an attack of bronchial asthma. In fact, her symptoms were so mild that her admission was granted mainly on account of the pitiful tale she told of poverty, sickness and want.

She endeavoured to commit suicide by cutting her throat with her table knife believing she was about to be discharged back to her destitute state, but Dr Godfrey was present and able to stop the bleeding with the aid of two nurses.

Her windpipe was penetrated and several large arteries injured. That night she appeared to be progressing satisfactorily, but her condition was still considered critical (The Age, 1891).

Dr Moloney and other doctors attended the Rev. J. L. Heffernan in his terminal illness with incurable pulmonary congestion (The Advocate, 1891b).

Dr Moloney attended Sarah A. Brown, a twenty four year old young woman who was employed as a cook and housemaid, shortly before she died. Moloney was of the opinion that she had influenza as there was a current local epidemic. She had been unwell for four days with chest pain and a headache. Sarah's brother was dissatisfied with Moloney's opinion and requested an inquest, but there is no record of an inquest in the press (Broadford Courier and Reedy Creek Times, 1891; The Ballarat Star 1891).

The Very Rev. Dr. Donaghy, V.G., Dean of St. Patrick's Cathedral collapsed unexpectedly and died. Dr. P. Moloney reached the dying priest's

bedside a few minutes before his death and was unable to save him (Advocate, 1891a).

D Moloney treated Captain Russell following an attack by one of his Nubian lions in a circus act. The lion Pacha throughout the performance had displayed the most evident signs of sullen ferocity, and when the trainer fell, immediately sprang upon him and was only frightened off by the point blank discharge of rifle.

Dr P Moloney found that the lions teeth had inflicted injuries of a most serious nature. On the right arm, just beneath the shoulder, between ten and twelve incised wounds were apparent, varying in depth from mere scratches to two inches The most dangerous wound had been caused by the lower canine tooth, which had penetrated the under portion of the arm to a depth of at least five inches, tearing the triceps in a terrible manner.

The wounds were stitched up, and last night the patient, though still confined to his room, was progressing very favourably still, in wounds of this character there is a certain danger of poisoning, bacterial infection or tetanus.

Russell was not sufficiently impressed with his treatment to pay Moloney's bill and was sued in court for £13 for medical attendance. An agreement of £12, with £3 3s costs was arrived at between the parties (Advocate, 1892; The Argus, 1893; Horsham Times, 1893; The Herald 6/3/1893a).

Dr Moloney assisted Dr Henry O'Hara in treating and operating on Madame D'Alba following a horrendous accident in a lift. The lift became stuck between two floors but as she was endeavouring to climb out it moved causing severe facial and skull trauma.

O'Hara appeared as her doctor at the subsequent litigation hearing and Moloney appears to have played little further part beyond treating the initial shock and haemorrhaging, and her recovery during the week after the accident (The Herald, 1893b; The Herald, 1894; Geelong Advertiser, 1894).

Moloney attended Mr Buckley suffering from a head injury sustained while walking along Spencer street, when a swinging Venetian

shutter struck him on the forehead, knocking him backward senseless. Moloney noted a slight wound on the forehead, but also concussion and a possible fracture of the skull requiring admission to hospital (Kyneton Observer, 1894).

Clinical Summary

The press reported fifty eight patients receiving care from Dr Moloney, thirty were accidents of whom three died, nineteen had medical conditions and twelve died, eight suffered violence, one from a lion, but only one died. Moloney had about this number under his care in hospital each month but the media prefers the more sensational crimes and accidents to a list of heart attacks and strokes.

Professional Positions and Medical Societies

Hibernian-Australasian Catholic Benefit Society

Dr Moloney was elected surgeon to the Hibernian-Australasian Catholic benefit society and re-elected on a yearly basis until his resignation in 1878 when he wrote to the Hibernian Australasian Catholic benefit society to tender his resignation and thanking them for their kindness and consideration to him while medical attendant to the branch.

The Society through the secretary thanked Dr. Moloney for his uniform kindness and attention to the members of this branch during the seven years he held the position of medical attendant to the branch (The Advocate, 1872; The Advocate, 1873; The Advocate, 1874b; The Advocate, 1874a; The Argus, 1875b; The Advocate, 1876; The Advocate, 1877b; The Advocate, 1877a; Advocate, 1878a; Advocate, 1878c).

Medical Society of Victoria

Dr Moloney was elected a member of the Medical Society of Victoria at the annual society meeting (The Argus, 1869).

Moloney read a paper about a case of poisoning by opium, treated by belladonna to the Medical

Society of Victoria on behalf of Dr. C. Smith who was unavoidably absent (The Age, 1870b).

Moloney read a paper about a case of traumatic tetanus, treated by the Calabar bean to the Medical Society of Victoria (The Argus, 1870a).

The annual dinner of the Medical Society of Victoria was attended by twenty five members and their guests. Dr Moloney responded to the usual toast to the Ladies in his usual eloquent manner and the party broke up about half-past eleven, after spending an exceedingly pleasant evening (The Argus, 1871).

Dr. Moloney will present the history of a case of carbolic acid poisoning at monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria. The case was also published by Moloney in the Australian Medical Journal under the heading "Poisoning by the External Use of Carbolic Acid" and deemed to be a valuable contribution, to the science of toxicology (The Argus, 1872c; The Argus, 1872a).

Dr. Ferguson presented the case of a little girl, aged about two to the Medical Society of Victoria, who had been bitten on the ankle by a tiger snake then treated for shock with intravenous injections of ammonia. Dr Moloney supported this argument though some traditionalists favoured the old ligature, cut and suck method (The Age, 1876b).

At the Medical Society of Victoria Annual Dinner, Dr. Moloney proposed his usual toast of "The Ladies" (The Argus, 1876b).

Dr Moloney initiated much discussion by expressing his opinion on the health benefits of tea to the Medical Society of Victoria. He stated that he had been obliged to give up tea for a time owing to its prejudicial effect upon his health but having discovered how to make it properly he was able to return to his ordinary custom of taking a cup or two with the morning meal. According to Dr Moloney all the mischief is caused by the tannin extracted by prolonged stewing of the leaf in hot water. Let the leaf be infused for only a few minutes he advised (The Argus, 1880b).

Dr Moloney was elected of the auditors at the annual meeting of the Medical Society

of Victoria, and one of the editors of the Australian Medical Journal (The Argus, 1881a; The Argus, 1883b).

The ordinary monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria elected Dr Jonasson a member of committee in place of Dr Moloney, who was already an ex officio member (The Argus, 1883c).

The annual meeting of this society Medical Society of Victoria noted that Dr. Moloney had retired from the editorship of the Australian Medical Journal (The Argus, 1884b).

The president of the Medical Society of Victoria, Dr. Haig, the two vice presidents, Drs Moloney and Turner, and the hon. secretary, Dr Allan all signed the following address in the name of the society to Edwin M. James, Esq., M.R.C.S., Eng., &c., surgeon to the Melbourne Hospital.

"We have the honour to inform you that, at a special meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria, held on Wednesday, April 9, 1884, the following resolution was unanimously carried :- 'That Mr E. M. James, ex-president of the Medical Society of Victoria, be requested to act as a representative of the society at all meetings of kindred associations during his visit to Europe and America.'"

The president in making the presentation, alluded in complimentary terms to Mr. James's thirty years' service at the Melbourne Hospital, and congratulated him on the respect and esteem he had gained both among the profession and the public during that period. Mr James suitably responded, and the meeting closed after drinking his health and wishing him a pleasant trip (The Argus, 1884a).

The ordinary monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria appointed Dr. Moloney as president elect for the coming year, being unopposed (The Age, 1884b).

Dr. Moloney was confirmed as elected president for the year at the annual meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria. There were now one hundred and seventy seven members, and the sixteen meetings which had been held during the year had been well attended.

The papers submitted for consideration were of great interest and the discussions evoked were frequently animated. The librarian reported that numerous additions had been made to the society's collection of books (The Age, 1885a).

Dr Moloney, as the president, chaired the ordinary monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria (The Argus, 1885c).

Dr. Moloney, the president chaired the ordinary monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria in which a number of pathological specimens were examined and discussed at length. Dr. Webb also exhibited a patient suffering from a peculiar form of aneurysm (The Age, 1885b; The Argus, 1885b).

Dr Moloney, as president, chaired the monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria. Dr 1 Owen read a paper on a case of poisoning by extract of eucalyptus the so called extract being apparently the volatile oil of the eucalyptus globules and numerous pathological specimens were exhibited by Dr. Williams, Mr Webb and Professor Allen (The Argus, 1885d).

Dr. Moloney, as president, chaired the monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria when he presented to the society an excellent copy of the picture commonly called 'The anatomy lesson.' Dr Charles Smith of Casterton and Dr J Williams presented some pathology specimens for examination.

Dr Moloney's valedictory address was organised for the forthcoming annual meeting in January (The Argus, 1885a).

Dr Moloney, as the retiring president, chaired The Medical Society of Victoria for the last time. The member proposed that he should represent the society at all kindred societies in Britain and Ireland during his approaching visit to those countries.

Moloney then read his retiring address He stated that the work of the society in the past year had been very satisfactory and then referred to the leading improvements and discoveries which had recently been made in medicine and surgery, alluding specially to Pasteur's discovery of the curableness of hydrophobia by vaccination. He urged the advisability of the removal of the

Melbourne Hospital, the Benevolent Asylum and the Women's Hospital to more suitable sites and also the removal of the Kew Asylum In connection with the lunatic asylum question the barrack system of treating lunatics was especially objected to.

A special compliment was paid to Mr Bosisto for his discoveries with reference to the value of the eucalyptus tree in medical science and regret was expressed that colonial plants were not more highly valued in a therapeutic aspect research. The architecture of Melbourne was condemned as not being suitable to the climate and the opinion was expressed that the Melbourne Harbor Trust ought not to have made Melbourne a seaport, but should have made Port Melbourne the port, the Sandridge bend and the piers being the proper place for docks and shipping.

A vote of thanks was passed to Dr Moloney for his address and the valuable services he had rendered to the society during the twelve months in which he had been its president (The Argus, 1886b).

The following is a portion of the address delivered by Dr. Moloney at the meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria on the occasion of his retiring from the presidency of the society, and reported in the Argus:

The present field of warfare in medical science is undoubtedly constituted by bacteriology. Not many years have elapsed since the bacillus of anthrax and the spirillum of relapsing fever were the only specific organisms generally recognised by English writers as proved sources of specific diseases.

But now every leading text-book of pathology includes an account of micro-organisms, their nature, mode of development and multiplication, their supposed classification, and the general laws which affect their life. It has been shown that bacteria abound in the soil upon which we tread, in the water which we drink, in the air which we breathe. They swarm in the alimentary canal and though many forms are comparatively or even absolutely innoxious, yet other forms have been more or less clearly connected with certain definite diseases. The method of fractional cultivation has

made us much more intimately acquainted with them than in earlier times.

A great number of apparently distinct species have now been isolated, and their powers have been tested by repeated inoculations of pure cultures, and in many instances the evidence seems satisfactory that certain specific organisms are the causes of certain specific diseases.

Into the nature of this evidence time will not allow me to enter. I can only allude to the efforts which are being made to discover some modes of protecting ourselves against the action of injurious micro-organisms, or of preventing or restraining their ill effects when already introduced into the body.

Very encouraging facts have now been known for a considerable time, which lead us to believe that some simple mode may yet be discovered of arresting the multiplication or of preventing the activity of micro-organisms within the blood or the tissues. Take for example the well-known experiments of Naegeli and Pasteur. Let moulds of yeast and bacteria all be present in a neutral saccharine fluid, and the bacteria alone flourish, causing lactic fermentation; add only one-half per cent. of tartaric acid, and the yeast will act so as to produce alcohol; increase the quantity of tartaric acid to four or five per cent, and moulds at once commence to grow.

Or take an even more familiar example in the must of grapes only the yeast fungi flourish;

but after a time the sugar is used up, and certain special bacteria then originate acetous

fermentation; as vinegar accumulates, moulds grow and consume the acetic acid; and at

last the ordinary bacteria of putrefaction are unopposed and set up their unsavoury process.

Such facts may nurse the hope that very slight and manageable alterations in the blood may absolutely inhibit the development of some of the most dreaded contagious diseases within the body. Till lately, however, little of practical value has been learnt concerning the actual prevention and arrest of disease, and as yet in only a restricted, if important, field. The proved power of certain antiseptics and disinfectants has been utilised in various ways as against our microscopic foes, but

hitherto with far more success outside the body than within the blood or the tissues; the known agents which control the development of disease germs must be present in certain definite strengths, the determination of which has occupied the attention of many great scientists; but these operative strengths are such as to prevent our utilising these known agents in a destructive war upon organisms developing in blood or in tissue. At present it does not seem likely that any ordinary disinfectant will be found which can be administered in such dose as to destroy the vitality or directly arrest the development of organisms within the body: it rather seems possible that some method may be discovered of altering the nature of the blood and nutrient fluids in some innocent manner, so as to render the body an unfit nidus for the growth of certain definite bacteria.

Hitherto successful results have only been obtained by inoculating animals with modified cultures of contagia, the animals then remaining protected from further infection for a variable time. Many methods of so modifying the various contagia have been devised, such as exposure to air or to heat, reduction of doses, artificial cultures in poor pabulum, inoculations in an unfavourable part of the body, or transfer through other animals. If the well-known bacilli of anthrax be cultivated in chicken broth for more than 20 days at 42deg. or 43deg. centigrade, they lose their virulence, and when inoculated into sheep and cattle they produce only a slight illness, which leaves the animals protected against malignant anthrax for about nine months or more.

If the bacilli of symptomatic anthrax, or quarter-evil, cultivated artificially, are injected in very small quantities under the skin of susceptible animals, a slight transient swelling follows, after which the animal is left protected against what would otherwise have been a fatal dose. Klein assures us that if the bacillus of swine plague is cultivated artificially and inoculated into other pigs, they suffer from a mild form of the disease which protects them subsequently from fatal attacks, but not from mild ones. The similar results obtained in smallpox are too familiar to need repetition.

Or if, again, the bacilli found in the septicaemia of mice, when purely cultivated, be inoculated in the back of the neck of a rabbit, death surely follows; but if the inoculation be made in the tip of the ear only a local inflammation ensues, after which the rabbit for several weeks is protected against fresh inoculation anywhere.

Very hopeful results have followed the transfer of pathogenic organisms through different animals. Thus, if malignant anthrax from sheep is inoculated into white mice, the latter die; but if their blood is then inoculated into other sheep, only a slight illness follows, and these sheep remain for a time protected against the virulent forms of anthrax. Ordinary vaccination as against smallpox is closely allied to this last-mentioned process, but it has not yet been clearly proved that vaccinia is true variola modified by passage through the cow. Such are some of the modes by which various experimenters have sought to find means of defending us from the inroads of our microscopic enemies, the bacteria.

Other modes, it may be, will be discovered. For example, it is known that different germs do not readily flourish side by side unless the food for them is very abundant. Directly a struggle for existence occurs the weaker ones perish, and, as has been pointed out already, very trifling circumstances in the nutrient medium may suffice to establish the growth of one particular organism and the inactivity or disappearance of others. Led on by this fact, attempts have recently been made to extirpate the bacillus tuberculosis from the lungs of phthisical patients by causing them to inhale the bacterium terre—the agent of ordinary putrefaction. Good results are said to have followed, but in this experiment there is obviously a radical mistake, inasmuch as the bacillus of tubercle grows abundantly in living tissue but can scarcely find natural conditions admitting of its growth outside the body.

The bacterium terre on the other hand flourishes freely outside the body; it is seen in great numbers in the fetid contents of phthisical cavities, but it cannot develop at all in living tissues. Hence these two germs grow in different soils, and cannot come into antagonism, and the special organism of putrefaction are scarcely the ones which should be

chosen for introduction into the interior of a phthisical lung.

Before leaving this subject, however, I must refer to the recent discovery of Pasteur, that, by one of the methods above mentioned, namely, that of exposure to air, the virus of hydrophobia may be mitigated or attenuated so that it may be inoculated without danger; and that, after repeated inoculations with such mitigated virus, an animal may be rendered secure against the fatal effects of the most deadly form of the poison.

It is to Pasteur, the eminent French savant, that we owe the most remarkable discovery in preventive medicine as yet published to the world. Not only from experiments on animals, but from the results of treatment in man, may we conclude that hydrophobia, the most fatal and certainly the most horrible of all diseases, has at length been cured. The method by which Pasteur arrived at his discovery, after patient experimentation for three years, is a lesson to inquirers, and, to use Tyndall's words, shows "the picture of a mind on which facts fall like germs upon a nutritive soil, and, like germs so favoured, undergo rapid increase and multiplication.

One hardly knows which to admire most, the intuitive vision which discerns in advance the new issues to which existing data point, or the skill in device, the adaptation of means to ends, whereby the intuition is brought to the test and ordeal of experiment."

It is interesting and creditable to the British School of Medicine to know that Pasteur, in his experiments, proceeded on the vaccine principle of our own Jenner; but in hydrophobia it was found,; after repeated trials, that not one or two, but several vaccinations were necessary for protection. The last case reported was that of a lad who had been bitten severely in several places by an undoubtedly rabid dog. Sixty hours afterwards the first subcutaneous injection of a very attenuated virus from the spinal cord of a hydrophobic rabbit was made, and daily afterwards a less and less attenuated injection was given for eleven times. This case, at the latest date heard of, that is three months after the bite, was still alive and well; and a second case, reported in November last, also promised to be a success.

When it is remembered that similar investigations by the same scientific genius had previously resulted in the discovery of a cure for splenic fever, for fowl cholera, and it might be added for pebrine, that disease in the silkworm, by which a sum equal to the milliards imposed as a tax by victorious Germany, was saved to France; -cheered by these splendid conquests into territory hitherto uninvaded. by science, the prevention or cure of diseases owing to animal or malarial septic poisons, appears to be near at hand, so that it is not an unreasonable hope that before long typhoid, diphtheria, malaria, scarlatina, and the whole list of the exanthemata and their allies will have lost their terrors and become preventable as well as curable.

Not in toto, of course; there are too many elements of error and mistake about disease and its surroundings, physical and personal, to let that millennium ever arrive, but a treatment like that of Pasteur's, which began with a precise division of micro-organism into aerobic and anaerobic, into germs which as in splenic fever, live by oxygen, and die without it, and germs as in septicaemia originate and live without oxygen, is now established on such firm experimental and therapeutic bases as to be confidently considered as only on the threshold of its vast achievements. Koch's discovery of the comma bacillus of cholera, though not yet quite established, is another feature of the past medical year, and more than suggests the hope that we are close reaching the fons et origo of that dread scourge, and of thus being able to keep it under hygienic control.

Anything relating to cholera has an especial interest for our colonists just now, owing to its importation a few weeks ago from the East into Brisbane, thus making it no longer a neglectable quantity in Australian nosology. The terrible lesson afforded by the ravages of cholera lately in unhygienic Italy, and still more unhygienic Spain should not be lost upon us. There poverty is the explanation, and to some extent the excuse of the march of contagion; but here, where there is practically no poverty at all, nor likely to be for many succeeding years-how can poverty exist in a country where labourers strike for eight hours and 10s. a day, we have still much to do in the way of preventive hygiene.

In a rich city like Melbourne-the ninth in population in the whole British empire-it is at once a surprise and a disgrace that there exists such a hotbed of disease as the West Melbourne Swamp; such an immense cultivation pool of germ-organisms as the Sandridge swamp; such seminaries for the nurture of septic poisons as the corporation tips; and within the heart of the city itself, those rookeries whose existence is revealed the ordinary citizen only when they become exposed before the erection of another palatial structure in our streets.

This leads us to the consideration of the situation of the hospitals, and other public charitable institutions in and about Melbourne. That the Benevolent Asylum is out of place and should be removed at once, goes without saying. It stops the traffic and paralyzes the growth of a very important, sub-metropolis. It exists, a nucleus of unformed and wasted city material on this very edge of the busiest streets in Hotham. When it is considered, too, that the sale of the ground would bring in a sufficient sum to purchase a site and build a place in a more removed and appropriate locality, there appears no reason to defend the location of the present incumbrance.

It is perhaps hardly right to speak with positiveness of institutions with which one has no connection beyond that of the general public, but there is little doubt that the Lying-in Hospital stands in great need of an improved hygiene, and when the directors of that institution become possessed of the thousands that their bizarre promises to bring they would do well to take thought whether it ever be possible to build on the present site, with justice to the patients or sanitary credit to themselves.

The: Kew Asylum again is conducted in violation of all recent knowledge of the treatment of lunatics. The cottage system, such as is the plan at Yarra Bend, should be adopted, and the housing of patients in large barracks cannot be too strongly condemned. The removal of the Melbourne Hospital or its retention on its present site is a subject that must be shortly and very definitely settled,

Much, no doubt,, may be advanced on, either side of the question, and it is matter for great regret

that the governing and professional bodies should at present be so far apart in opinion, but I feel sure that with, on the part of. the committee, so much sincere anxiety for the welfare of the institution, so much of the representative intellect of our citizens in its personnel, that a modus locandi is by no means impossible to arrange with the honorary staff who are as sincere in their anxiety for the patients as the committee, and whose opinions are at least of not less value. I quite confess I am quite with my colleagues on the desirability of removal. The value of the land, if sold, the effect on trade and traffic of its removal, the business knowledge of the committee can appreciate better than we, but from a medical, and especially surgical aspect, the transfer of the hospital to a locality of preference about a. mile northwards is greatly to be wished-indeed, I am confident an absolute necessity.

The bed accommodation is now considerably less than when I was a resident several years ago, though the city has greatly enlarged, patients of the very class for whom the hospital exists have to be refused admission, and in fact the building itself is such as many lesser cities in Europe would not tolerate, and no one with a knowledge of modern hospital requirements would not allow was far behind this progressive time in every particular of arrangements and construction.

Should the sale of the present site not bring a sufficient sum (which authoritative appraisers of city property deny) to build an institution of the completeness and magnificence which Melbourne should possess, an appeal to the notably charitable Victorian public would, it is certain, result in enough not only for the mere buildings, but for funds to provide for the complete recovery of convalescents, who have now to be discharged half cured, with the near possibility of relapse, instead of the near assuredness of perfect health which a stay in some affiliated sanatorium would afford.

The warm interest taken by the Premier, Mr. Service, in the object of the deputation of the Melbourne Hospital staff, and the presence of the Parliamentary representatives of East and West Melbourne, give abundant proof that Parliament, which has hitherto done so little for

the medical profession, is amenable to rational statement, and requires only to the roughly know

our necessities to help us. There appears to be among British communities an existent belief that medical men are unsuitable for Parliament, whilst on the Continent, notably France and Germany; the medical element has not been the least of the motor powers of the government of the State.

Many names might be adduced from the French Chamber of Representatives, and in Germany, to take one instance alone, the illustrious Virchow is known to have commanded the greatest respect in the Legislative Chamber. Let us hope that before long our profession will have many real representatives of our wants and wishes, which are really those of the public, in Parliament. They will have to be men who have already made their mark in the profession, perhaps through some specialty, or under any circumstances so situated as to be able to represent the profession on questions of sanitation and hygiene.

A Minister of Health is surely as much a necessity as a Minister of Customs, whose behaviour is regulated merely by his officials. The previous mention of architecture reminds me that we could be said, till lately, hardly to possess a building, public or private, which is climatically suitable. For suburban private houses, a broad veranda to north and west is an absolute necessity against the summer, and the building of one-storied houses should be considered a hygienic crime, especially when it is so noticeable that as much money is wasted on cumbrous and meaningless decoration as would add another storey to the house.

All medical practitioners know that patients do better up-stairs than down, and it is no exaggeration to say that every additional storey to a building in and about the city is practically equal to placing it another mile from town (The Bacchus Marsh Express, 1886).

The Editorial in the Argus was impressed with the content of Moloney's address as follows:-In one respect the address of Dr. Moloney, the retiring president to the Medical Society, was a paean of triumph. The era of medical discovery still continues. During the past year great activity has been manifested in every department, especially in the study of those germs which are now widely believed to be the causes of disease. The new method of investigating the origin of

sickness, with a view to its prevention, is fast relieving medicine from the often-repeated taunt that its treatment was based upon lucky guesses.

The conjectural remedies which once prevailed, are disappearing, and it would now be impossible to satirise the profession as LE SAGE did in his description of the Spanish doctor, whose one cure for every ailment was water.

Pasteur and Koch have carried their experiments on germs to such a pitch that many diseases can be warded off by simple means. Hydrophobia, it is, said, will cease to be a terror, and cholera will no longer be a scourge Dr Moloney goes even further, and holds out the hope that, as science progresses, the ravages effected by these little organisms will be altogether prevented, and fevers and diphtheria become as much a matter of history as the Black Death (The Argus, 1886c).

A medical colleague, Chas. L. Iredell, was impressed by Moloney's address except where he criticised the increasing specialisation in medicine and wrote:-it is a great pity that Dr. Moloney's otherwise excellent address should have been marred by an attack on a portion of his fellow workers' members of his own profession, a profession which should by reason of its common, interest work in unison, as it seems to me to be both unjust and uncalled for (The Argus, 1886d).

John Backhouse, a resident surgeon at the Alfred Hospital, also criticised Molony for stating that nursing was one of the unsatisfactory features in colonial life and states that an institution in which a thorough trained, capable nurse can be got without delay was essential writing as follows:-'I know not for what reason Dr Moloney should entirely ignore the nurses' training school at this institution, which has existed for about six years, and now has reached a high place in public estimation. The certificated nurses from this Hospital can hold their own in their profession against nurses trained in this old country, as they have passed through a thorough course of practical training' (The Argus, 1886a).

The ordinary monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria elected Dr Jonasson a

member of committee in place of Dr Moloney, who was already an ex officio member (The Argus, 1887f).

Dr. Moloney attended the Medical Society of Victoria meeting and, on presenting debentures and money to the amount of £25, became a life member of the society.

Dr. J. W. D Hooper, read a paper on some practical points in the diagnosis and treatment of puerperal septicaemia. Dr. Homnan read notes of a case of injury to the kidney and exhibited a specimen in illustration. Both papers were followed by animated discussions. Dr. G. A. Syme exhibited several pathological specimens (The Age, 1887b).

Dr. Moloney exhibited a patient suffering from a tumour in the neck to the ordinary meeting of about thirty members of the Medical Society of Victoria (Age, 1888a).

Other Societies and Positions

Dr. Moloney was appointed acting medical officer to the Immigration Hospital and Industrial Schools by The Chief Secretary (The Argus, 1872c).

Dr. Moloney, in the absence of Dr. M'Gaurin, visited the hospital of the principal school for girls at the St. Kilda military barracks regularly every day (The Age, 1872b).

Moloney was reported to be a member of the Convent of Mercy charitable organization (The Argus, 1875a).

The St. Vincent de Paul Boys' Orphanage gratefully mentioned that Dr. P. Moloney kindly and promptly attended to any case requiring surgical aid (Advocate, 1878b).

Dr. Moloney put his name forward as a candidate for the seat at the council of the Melbourne University rendered vacant by the death of Dr. Rose. Dr. Moloney based his application on the grounds that the scholastic profession is already fully represented in the council, that the death of Dr. Rose leaves a vacancy in the medical representation which he may fairly claim and that as a graduate of the university, he belongs to a class at present very

inadequately represented at the council board (The Argus, 1878c).

Dr Moloney made some comments on a lecture on the " Perception of Colour, read by Dr Jamieson at a special meeting of the members of the Royal Society of Victoria (The Argus, 1878d).

Dr. Moloney was elected by ballot as one of three departmental editors of the Australian Medical Journal (The Argus, 1879a).

Dr. Moloney exhibited and described a new cupping instrument invented by himself at the Medical Society of Victoria's ordinary monthly meeting (The Age, 1879b).

Dr. Moloney exhibited Esmarch's Triangular Bandage at the monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria, one advantage of which is that diagrams are printed upon it showing the manner of using it (The Age, 1879a; The Argus, 1879b).

Dr. Moloney was one of the candidates for the vacancy as the chair of materia medica and therapeutics at the University (The Age, 1881b; The Argus, 1881b).

Dr Moloney was elected one of the councillors at the seventh annual meeting of the Australian Health at the Town Hall. He pleaded for moderation in athletic exercises (The Argus, 1882c).

Lectures and Opinions

Dr. Moloney gave the first of two lectures on anatomy of the human body to the students in training, and the members of the elementary and advanced classes in gymnastics at the request of the instructor of the National Gymnasium having suggested the desirability of a few medical lectures (The Argus, 1870c).

Dr. Moloney, resident surgeon of the Melbourne Hospital and Mr. W. Carey Rees, the resident medical officer of the Alfred Hospital and Moloney's fellow first graduate from the Melbourne Medical School,, gave the highest praise to a solution of the chloride of aluminium as a medicine produced by new process by Mr. Cosmo Newbery and Mr. W. Johnson (The Australasian, 1871).

In 1873, Moloney appeared in inquests on deceased subjects on two occasions, both dying of alcoholism, and he made one speech at a social gathering. He set up in private practice in Lonsdale Street in 1874 and later moved to 106 Collins Street East.

Dr. Moloney stated strong approval for a new disinfectant called Labarraques, a concentrated solution of chloride of soda, used as a deodoriser, for the sick room and for Sanatory Lying-in-Hospital purposes, generally just brought into the Melbourne market, and manufactured by Messrs. M. O'Reilly and On, Nicholson Street (The Age, 1874).

The press noted that most doctors had their favoured therapy for scarlet fever, Moloney prescribed carbolic acid, chloric ether, and opium plus the wet sheet if patients would submit to it, while Dr. Rees considers the ozonised oil treatment valuable, but prescribes perchloride of iron and the intravenous injection of ammonia as well. The clear implication being that none knew for certain what was effective (The Age, 1876a; Leader, 1876).

Moloney was enlisted by the Melbourne Punch to answer correspondents questions and wrote obscurely that 'It is quite possible that the hypodermic injection of a mania will cure a person of madness, but we never heard of a properly authenticated case. Ask Halford' (Melbourne Punch, 1877).

Dr. Moloney gave an interesting lecture on Mistakes in Regard to Health in the hall of the Mechanics' Institute. Do not however consider this may have concerned mistakes made by doctors, perish the thought. The lecture concerned errors made by members of the community in caring for their health with regard to such as boots and cold baths. He touched upon some of the prevailing habits of society and referred in sarcastic terms to the folly of some of the fashions. True to his Irish nationality and doctors' habits, Moloney advised that 'A quick darting pain under the left shoulder-blade is best treated with a dark brandy and soda, at 7.30 a.m. daily. Let this dose be repeated very frequently, if the cellar will run to it,' and that claret was the safest beverage that

could be used. At the conclusion of his lecture, Dr Moloney was accorded a warm vote of thanks by the numerous audience, who had listened attentively to his instructive remarks (The Age, 1878; The Argus, 1878a; Melbourne Punch, 1878).

Dr Moloney addressed the Melbourne Social Science Congress disagreeing with the previous speaker who stated that the Melbourne Hospital was being greatly abused. In his own experience he had found the greatest difficulty in inducing people to go into the hospital. It must be remembered that the hospital served a variety of purposes apart from those ordinarily appertaining to a hospital. It was a refuge for the destitute and was also a hospital for incurables (The Argus, 1880a).

Moloney was mocked in the press for appearing to suggest that the elixir of life had been discovered when we have the authority of Dr. Moloney that a man might live five hundred years if constantly travelling forwards and backwards between here and Europe, taking care to keep his blood in spring condition. It was a great downfall to learn that all the doctor meant to convey was that travel was beneficial to the health. We knew that before (Kilmore Free Press, 1882).

Dr Moloney read a paper based on the cure of consumption as illustrated by the case of Mr Cook and the effect of breaking his ribs in the Jolimont accident. Moloney suggested the accident did him a favour! While Moloney may have stumbled fortuitously on the benefits of pneumothorax for TB, Dr James Carson had described this much earlier in 1820. Moloney suggested other treatments for other diseases by fracturing bones, Dr Youl warned him that this may lead to a coroner's inquest with a jury's decision of murder or manslaughter.

Moloney as always had the last word suggesting he try his cure for consumption on Dr. Youl (Melbourne Punch, 1882).

Dr Moloney expressed his opinion on cycling stating that he would give anything to be able to run out of the city into the fresh air for half an hour. The paper implied the Union of Cyclists

would welcome his company and suggested he obtain a tricycle (The Australasian, 1882)!

The Leader commented favourably on the August issue of the Australian Medical Journal which it considered always interesting to intelligent laymen. The most interesting topic was a paper on a most seasonable topic, Bronchial Catarrh or Bronchial Pneumonia, read by Dr. Moloney at the last monthly meeting of the Medical Society.

The writer indicated how fatal recently the epidemic he described had been in Victoria, especially among young and elderly persons, and enumerates remedies which he found notably effective (The Leader, 1885).

Dr. Moloney read a paper on the ill effects of cigarette smoking at the first annual meeting of the Melbourne Medical Association, a man ahead of his time (The Age, 1892).

Dr Moloney expressed his opinion supporting a report submitted by Dr. Gresswell on the subject of infant life protection and the appointment of qualified nurses as inspectors of Foundling Houses, at a meeting of the Board of Public Health (The Herald, 1892b).

Advances at St Vincent's were reported with a not quite serious or accurate description of a new traction device designed by Moloney. It was a hideous triangular structure, from which, by the aid of straps and pulleys, he literally hangs a man by the neck for several minutes causing partial paralysis of the limbs (Advocate, 1894)!

Societies and Social Events

Mr. James Moloney, a brother of Dr. Moloney, commenced practice as a solicitor in Melbourne (The Bacchus Marsh, 1876).

Moloney spoke at the Australian Health Society meeting on the difficulty of obtaining a sufficiency of suitable nurses. It was considered the most useful and practical instruction for nurses was given at the bedside in a hospital. The need for a home for the nurses based near the hospital was also discussed (Weekly Times, 1880).

Dr. P. Moloney was re-elected as a member of the Australian Health Society committee (The Australasian, 1881).

Dr. Moloney met with an accident when the wheels of his carriage fell off and he was thrown out. Though severely shaken he was not injured (Advocate, 1885a).

Dr and Mrs Moloney had another accident in their buggy in which the wheels got caught in a tramline groove. Both were thrown out and Mrs Maloney suffered a broken rib, but the doctor escaped injury (Riverina Herald, 1886).

The Advocate published a letter praising the choice of Dr Moloney, described as a skilful physician and a genial and thoroughly patriotic Irishman, as a representative of this country (Advocate, 1886).

A meeting was held to commemorate the twenty sixth anniversary of the opening of the medical school. The presence of female students was welcomed. Eminent university figures gave speeches mentioning professors and alumni including Dr. Moloney as the first of two graduates. He beamed with pleasure in the centre of the hall, and did not rise to respond (The Argus, 1887d)!

Dr. Moloney was offered the positions of clinical lecturer in medicine at the University Council meeting (The Age, 1887c).

Dr. Moloney, as president, chaired the fortnightly meeting of the Medical Students Society at the Melbourne Hospital. Mr Goodall moved 'That the society affirm the principle that the lecturers on medicine and surgery at the Medical School should be members of the Melbourne Hospital staff.' It was also proposed that the University Club should have a central club house, a concept strongly advocated by Dr Moloney (The Argus, 1887e).

Dr Moloney attended a meeting of members of the medical profession at the Atheneum to present an address of congratulation to Dr Brownless, upon the occasion of his election to the office of chancellor of the University of Melbourne (The Argus, 1887b).

The council of the University of Melbourne meeting announced that plans and specifications for the natural philosophy theatre and laboratories and the biological theatre and laboratories would be completed this week and proposed asking for tenders.

Dr Moloney said that there was no money available at present for the whole of this work but the council might proceed with the erection of the biologic theatre and laboratories for which the Government had placed a sum on the estimates. He moved that tenders be called for the motor car theatre and laboratories. Dr Moloney was re-appointed clinical lecturer in medicine (The Argus, 1887g).

The Age advertised the return of Dr. Moloney to practise his profession in Melbourne, though details of his absence were not given unless it was to Hobart (The Age, 1887b).

His Excellency the Governor opened the Intercolonial Medical Congress with the following statement, one of significant relevance to developments in global medicine and specifically to Victorian medicine in which Moloney was a leading figure.

‘Mr. President and Gentlemen,—Your meeting here in congress is one of the most important of the many very interesting events that will make this period remarkable in the history of Australasia. The result of this congress will be, I venture to believe, as greatly to the advantage of medical science throughout Europe and America as it will be productive of great good in the country in which it has assembled. Eminent medical gentlemen have come from India and distant countries, as well as from all parts of Australia, to take part in the deliberations of this meeting, men whose reputation as medical scientists will give to the papers which they will submit to the congress a position of commanding influence upon some of the greatest medical questions of the day.

The range of work that comes within the compass of medical science is so vast that no one mind can grasp and treat in an exhaustive manner the several branches in all their varied bearings, while in the busy walks of practical life few medical men can afford the time requisite

for a close examination of more than one or two subjects of special study.

These meetings are, therefore, of untold value, where the mental wealth acquired by individual scientists is collectively submitted to the critical analysis of their fellow workers, whose education, experienced observation and general knowledge properly fit them to discuss, consider and estimate at their proper value the deductions that may with safety be drawn from the careful investigation of the specialist. The amount of work which the preparation for a meeting of this character entails can only be adequately appreciated when we reflect that the papers to be read are the outcome of years of unremitting study and observation, devoted to the successful attainment of the noblest end to which the greatest intellects can be applied—the amelioration of human suffering in all its varieties and forms of misery, and thus indirectly to the strengthening and development of the brain power of the world, on which the ever growing requirements of the day make an ever increasing demand. It is, perhaps, a fitting close to the rejoicings with which the completion of the centennial of Australasia has been commemorated that this congress should be now assembled in Melbourne.

The past 100 years are replete with historic events which have created a British Empire in the southern hemisphere. But marvellous as has been the progress which has led to this development, it is not so marvellous as the advance that has been made during the same period in the knowledge and application of medical science. And if the experience of the past hundred years may be accepted as being any guide as to what the discoveries may be in the future, then those who may hope to live for the next thirty or forty years may revel in intellectual anticipations as to what they may then know and witness, while the principal objects for which the medical congress has assembled will without doubt receive every consideration and be kept carefully in view. I trust the members will likewise accept my assurance that it is our anxious desire to offer to all our most cordial welcome, whether they come from distant lands, from sister colonies, or from our own country

districts, as also to those whose familiar faces we gladly recognise as belonging to our own immediate neighbourhood.

And I venture to submit as my personal medical contribution for the consideration of this great congress the proposition, which I trust may be carried without a dissentient voice, that health is largely promoted by a well-proportioned amount of relaxation and enjoyment of this world's pleasures. And I am not sure whether the rule advocated in this colony—eight hours' work, eight hours' sleep, eight hours' play—should not be adopted by this congress as that great panacea against all ills.

I trust I may be permitted to congratulate Mr. Fitzgerald whose untiring efforts have in so large a measure contributed to bringing together so many eminent gentlemen upon what I may safely, in anticipation, call this very successful meeting of the medical congress. And I congratulate myself upon its being one of the happy incidents connected with the position I have the honour to occupy in this colony, that I am permitted to be so far connected with this great and important meeting as to have been requested to perform the duty of declaring the medical congress open, a duty which I have now the honour to fulfil, with the most sincere and heartfelt good wishes that the result of its deliberations may tend to the advancement of science and to the benefit of mankind.

Professor Allen, the general secretary, thanked his fellow members of the organising committee including Dr. Moloney (The Age, 1889; The Argus, 1889a).

Dr Moloney and Mr. J. H White delivered lectures before a very large attendance in the Academy of Music. White's talk was entitled "Why is Hobson's Bay Neglected" (The Argus, 1889c).

Dr Moloney spoke of the proposal of the West Melbourne docks from a public health point of view, stating that the proposal to have docks at West Melbourne was, in its sanitary sense, appalling. They would form a Government farm of typhoid and cholera (The Argus, 1889c).

Moloney joined a group to improve the construction and sanitation of the docks at Hobson's bay. Not much seems to have happened over two months according to the Standard.

Dr Moloney once expressed his opinion that the West Melbourne Docks were unsanitary and would have an adverse effect on the health of Melbourne citizens. A current editorial supported that opinion and criticised the city management for a lack of activity to improve the cleanliness of the area (Williamstown Chronicle, 1890b; Standard, 1890).

Dr Moloney and others attended a lecture illustrated with diagrams on a blackboard. by Dr. Springthorpe on the use of the lymph for TB, the Koch cure. Springthorpe then demonstrated the cure by injecting lymph into the back of two patients. The outcome and subsequent benefits were not stated (Weekly Time, 1891).

Drs P Moloney was elected president at the meeting of the Melbourne Medical Association (The Argus, 1891b).

Dr Moloney wants Railway Commissioners salaries reduced. How about that £300 a year, Doctor (The Herald, 1890b)?

Some Misdemeanours

Two compliments to commence this section.

Mr, Cohen, the committee treasurer, remarked that they had never had a resident surgeon of more ability and promise than Dr. Moloney. He believed that although Dr. Moloney had been sometimes absent, he never in a single instance neglected a patient (The Age, 1872a).

John Madden, a fellow student at St Patrick's College, described Moloney's more serious side: 'His inmost instinct was towards poetic gentleness, and abstract philosophy, and, as he grew older, his leisure and recreation were sought in these directions to the exclusion of the more active and material pursuit of his profession and in no way was this more displayed than in detecting the philosophy underlying extravagances of human character by the light of humour. He was gentle and generous always and so free from any egotism that I think

the successes of his friends gladdened him more than his own great one' (Nairn, & Serle, 1986).

An extensive series of articles in the press referred to the recent outbreak of diphtheria in which three people died including one Melbourne Hospital Nurse after caring for one of the other cases. Apparently Nurse Carter complained that she was neglected by the other nursing staff prior to her demise according to a report by Dr. Forster.

The Nurse was in Dr Moloney's ward. Forster asked Moloney if she may be administered champagne as a comfort measure. Moloney agreed with this and prescribed regular painting of her throat. Neither were given nor the milk she requested. Dr Forster was denied admission to her ward by a porter acting on behalf on Dr Molloy, the superintendent, provoking some acrimonious exchange in the press.

Dr Moloney was accused of neglect of Nurse Carter. Mr Arundel Carter, the coroner for the county of Middlesex, England, referring to the death of his sister, the above nurse in the Melbourne Hospital who died in August last from diphtheria, and stating that from the reports he had received from independent persons he was obliged to come to the conclusion that the deceased had been neglected whilst ill.

The writer said his relative had complained of want of sufficient nourishment and added that he had also received reports of the lack of attention on the part of the hospital staff.

Dr Moloney, who attended the case, said that there had been no neglect and that he was quite satisfied that the nurse had received every care. Dr Morton, the resident surgeon, informed the committee that he had visited the patient half a dozen times a day, and Dr Moloney, in whose care she was, had visited her three or four times daily.

A letter was read from the chairman saying the matter had been fully inquired into at the time. It was resolved to send the doctors reports to the writer, and also the report of the autopsy. There may be no negligence here. Moloney appears to emerge with an unsullied reputation for events

on his watch after deflecting disapproval by suggesting a separate building for diphtheria patients, though the nurses were widely criticised. As medical men and women we owe it to our colleagues to ensure personally they receive the optimal care (The Herald, 1890c; The Herald, 1890d; The Ballarat Star, 1890; The Herald, 1890e; The Herald, 1890f; Argus, 1891a; Advocate, 1891c).

A serious charge was brought by the medical students against Dr Moloney, one of the honorary physicians. They complained to the committee that, though they have been attending regularly since April 1st, Moloney has not attended once to give them that clinical instruction for which they had to pay him fees to the amount of £4 10s each. It appeared that in fact Dr Moloney had only attended at the hospital for five hours during the whole of the past month.

The committee awaited the receipt of an explanation from Dr Moloney. It was resolved to appoint an additional medical officer at £150 per annum.

Dr. Moloney wrote in reference to the complaints that had been made against him, to the effect that for some time past he had found it more convenient to visit the hospital in the afternoon, and he was under the impression that the students had arranged to attend the clinical lectures of the other physicians. However, in reply to a letter from some of the fourth year students, he would make arrangements for regularly resuming his morning attendances. For the past three weeks he had been able to attend in the forenoon, and he declared to say that he would always be glad to assist the committee in furthering the interests of the hospital.

This is unimpressive for a man who superficially is an enthusiastic supporter of the University, the Medical School and education as a whole, a man who applied for and expected a position as a university lecturer.

He should have discovered what was happening with student teaching rather than assume it was happening. The allegation that he only attended public patients for five hours a month when he has dozens of patients under his care is appalling.

It was not further pursued or commented upon (The Argus, 1884d; Leader, 1884; The Argus, 1884c; The Age, 1884d).

Dr P. Moloney criticised a medical colleague at the inquest into the death by drowning of Michael O'Brien, implying that the treatment by Dr Crowley was not so complete as it might have been, and that some slight delay took place. Dr Molloy, the medical superintendent denied the statements of Dr Moloney at the inquest and afterwards wrote to the president of the Hospital Committee with reference to the subject.

This resulted in the House Committee holding a special meeting chaired by the President, Mr F. Godfrey to deal with the matter. Drs Moloney, Molloy, and Crowley were also in attendance. The house committee find that there was no delay or improper treatment by Dr. Crowley in dealing with the case of Michael O'Brien, and completely exonerated him from all blame. They also expressed regret that if Dr Moloney entertained the opinion he expressed at the inquest that he did not refrain from expressing it at that place, and that he might instead have communicated it to the Hospital Committee (The Herald, 1892a).

This is a significant reprimand for unprofessional behaviour, a clear indication the Moloney's sense of self-importance exceeded his professional ethics. Finding fault with a colleague in public is unacceptable behaviour, especially when your allegations are baseless.

Conclusion

Most information indicates Moloney was a highly respected competent doctor. A polymath well versed in the arts as well as the latest medical science. Moloney also had a habit of delving into political issues in the midst of excellent medical lectures including criticising the location of the Melbourne Hospital, erroneously criticising the lack of a training school for nurses and criticising the inevitable increasing specialisation in medicine. He also criticised a professional colleague publicly but erroneously.

Moloney's parting lecture to the Medical Society of Victoria, more than any information

discovered in this research about him, clearly demonstrates an extremely well informed doctor with extensive up to date knowledge in the area of infectious diseases, but also one who tactlessly favours his opinion even if it is frankly incorrect or upsets other colleagues.

References

- Broadford Courier and Reedy Creek Times.* (1891, September 19).
- Colac Herald.* (1889, January 1).
- Geelong Advertiser.* (1870, July 6).
- Geelong Advertiser.* (1878, May 25).
- Geelong Advertiser.* (1888, December 1).
- Geelong Advertiser.* (1894, October 5).
- Gippsland Mercury.* (1881, November 8).
- Herald.* (1889, November 1).
- Horsham Times.* (1893, January 27).
- Illustrated Australian News.* (1881, September 7).
- Kilmore Free Press.* (1882, March 23).
- Kilmore Free Press.* (1886, May 20).
- Kyneton Observer.* (1894, July 17).
- Leader.* (1876, July 3).
- Leader.* (1884, May 24).
- Leader.* (1890, May 3).
- Melbourne Punch.* (1877, January 11).
- Melbourne Punch.* (1878a, August 1).
- Melbourne Punch.* (1878b, December 12).
- Melbourne Punch.* (1882, June 1).
- Mercury and Weekly Courier.* (1878, June 29).
- Nairn, B., & Serle, G. (1986). Patrick Moloney. In *Australian Dictionary of Biography* (Vol. 5). National Centre of Biography, Australian National University. Retrieved from <https://adb.anu.edu.au/biography/moloney-patrick-4219>
- Riverina Herald.* (1886, January 22).
- Sportsman.* (1883, November 28).

- Sportsman*. (1884, December 17).
- Standard*. (1890, July 19).
- Stride, P. (2015). Kalgoorlie Hospital, Western Australia 1895–1897: The first five months of hospital admissions, and typhoid in the gold fields. *Journal of Environmental and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 1–16.
- The Advocate*. (1872, June 29).
- The Advocate*. (1873, June 14).
- The Advocate*. (1874a, December 26).
- The Advocate*. (1874b, January 3).
- The Advocate*. (1876, December 23).
- The Advocate*. (1877a, December 22).
- The Advocate*. (1877b, June 23).
- The Advocate*. (1878a, April 13).
- The Advocate*. (1878b, March 30).
- The Advocate*. (1878c, September 14).
- The Advocate*. (1879, January 4).
- The Advocate*. (1885a, April 25).
- The Advocate*. (1885b, June 13).
- The Advocate*. (1886, February 20).
- The Advocate*. (1887, March 19).
- The Advocate*. (1891a, December 12).
- The Advocate*. (1891b, July 11).
- The Advocate*. (1891c, October 1).
- The Advocate*. (1892, December 17).
- The Advocate*. (1894, January 20).
- The Age*. (1870a, August 5).
- The Age*. (1870b, June 9).
- The Age*. (1872a, January 3).
- The Age*. (1872b, May 13).
- The Age*. (1874, November 28).
- The Age*. (1876a, July 3).
- The Age*. (1876b, July 6).
- The Age*. (1876c, July 6).
- The Age*. (1878, July 23).
- The Age*. (1879a, August 9).
- The Age*. (1879b, July 5).
- The Age*. (1881a, August 31).
- The Age*. (1881b, November 21).
- The Age*. (1882a, December 5).
- The Age*. (1882b, December 5).
- The Age*. (1882c, February 24).
- The Age*. (1884a, April 5).
- The Age*. (1884b, December 17).
- The Age*. (1884, June 18).
- The Age*. (1884c, June 28).
- The Age*. (1884d, September 13).
- The Age*. (1885a, January 15).
- The Age*. (1885b, June 6).
- The Age*. (1885c, October 19).
- The Age*. (1887a, April 25).
- The Age*. (1887b, July 11).
- The Age*. (1887c, May 3).
- The Age*. (1887d, November 4).
- The Age*. (1888a, December 10).
- The Age*. (1888b, January 6).
- The Age*. (1889, January 8).
- The Age*. (1890, April 19).
- The Age*. (1891, June 27).
- The Age*. (1892, July 1).
- The Argus*. (1869, January 14).
- The Argus*. (1870a, August 5).
- The Argus*. (1870b, August 6).
- The Argus*. (1870c, June 17).
- The Argus*. (1871, November 16).
- The Argus*. (1872a, April 1).
- The Argus*. (1872b, August 26).
- The Argus*. (1872c, March 6).
- The Argus*. (1872d, March 8).
- The Argus*. (1873, December 6).

- The Argus*. (1875a, July 28).
The Argus. (1875b, June 12).
The Argus. (1876a, July 21).
The Argus. (1876b, October 26).
The Argus. (1878a, July 24).
The Argus. (1878,b June 25).
The Argus. (1878c, June 3).
The Argus. (1878d, October 18).
The Argus. (1879a, April 5).
The Argus. (1879b, August 9).
The Argus. (1880a, December 11).
The Argus. (1880b, October 23).
The Argus. (1881a, January 13).
The Argus. (1881b, November 21).
The Argus. (1881c, September 1).
The Argus. (1881d, September 20).
The Argus. (1882a, December 7).
The Argus. (1882b, December 9).
The Argus. (1882c, September 28).
The Argus. (1883a, August 29).
The Argus. (1883b, January 15).
The Argus. (1883c, May 7).
The Argus. (1884a, April 16).
The Argus. (1884b, January 10).
The Argus. (1884c, June 4).
The Argus. (1884d, May 21).
The Argus. (1885a, December 7).
The Argus. (1885b, June 6).
The Argus. (1885c, May 9).
The Argus. (1885d, September 8).
The Argus. (1886a, February 1).
The Argus. (1886b, January 14).
The Argus. (1886c, January 25).
The Argus. (1886d, January 26).
The Argus. (1887a, April 25).
The Argus. (1887b, July 22).
The Argus. (1887c, June 18).
The Argus. (1887d, March 23).
The Argus. (1887e, May 21).
The Argus. (1887f, May 7).
The Argus. (1887g, September 6).
The Argus. (1888, September 21).
The Argus. (1889a, January 8).
The Argus. (1889b, March 8).
The Argus. (1889c, November 2).
The Argus. (1889d, November 2).
The Argus. (1890, August 7).
The Argus. (1891a, January 7).
The Argus. (1891b, May 20).
The Argus. (1893, January 24).
The Australasian. (1870, October 29).
The Australasian. (1871, July 22).
The Australasian. (1877, November 24).
The Australasian. (1881, October 1).
The Australasian. (1882, October 7).
The Australasian. (1885, April 4).
The Australasian. (1889, March 9).
The Bacchus Marsh Express. (1886, February 6).
The Bacchus Marsh. (1876, May 6).
The Ballarat Star. (1890, January 17).
The Ballarat Star. (1891, September 15).
The Herald. (1867, May 11).
The Herald. (1868, June 3).
The Herald. (1870, July 11).
The Herald. (1877, November 26).
The Herald. (1878a, December 13).
The Herald. (1878b, November 23).
The Herald. (1879, May 1).
The Herald. (1880, March 18).
The Herald. (1882, April 18).

- The Herald*. (1884a, July 1).
The Herald. (1884b, June 21).
The Herald. (1884c, May 20).
The Herald. (1887, April 4).
The Herald. (1890a, August 4).
The Herald. (1890b, December 17).
The Herald. (1890c, September 13).
The Herald. (1890d, September 15).
The Herald. (1890e, September 17).
The Herald. (1890f, September 18).
The Herald. (1892a, February 13).
The Herald. (1892b, November 23).
The Herald. (1893a, March 6).
The Herald. (1893b, May 28).
The Herald. (1894, October 5).
The Leader. (1882, December 9).
The Leader. (1885, August 29).
The Riverina Herald. (1869, September 15).
The Riverina Herald. (1884, June 21).
The Telegraph, St Kilda, Praban and South Yarra Guardian. (1874, November 7).
Weekly Times. (1869, September 25).
Weekly Times. (1870, August 20).
Weekly Times. (1874, November 7).
Weekly Times. (1880, April 24).
Weekly Times. (1882, February 25).
Weekly Times. (1887, March 19).
Weekly Times. (1890a, April 12).
Weekly Times. (1890b, March 29).
Weekly Times. (1891, March 21).
Williamstown Chronicle. (1878, November 23).
Williamstown Chronicle. (1890a, April 19).
Williamstown Chronicle. (1890b, May 10).